

Gamification For Learning English to Improve Pronunciation With Automatic Speech Recognition

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Abstract— Smartphone usage among Indonesian students is high to the point it can be considered an addiction, as there were many students who underestimated their obligations to study English as international language. One of the solutions provided is to build smartphone games that can benefit the players. To overcome this problem, a game called "The Demite" will be built in this study, which will provide solutions not only as a means of entertainment, but also as a means of learning in pronunciation of English words. This game is a casual-horror genre with a location-based, augmented reality, and speech recognition feature that requires player to capture and fight ghosts by saying English words that appear with the right pronunciation. Based on the results of the implementation obtained, main scenario in the design of The Demite has been successfully implemented. The results of the student questionnaire analysis showed that the average assessment for aesthetic, learnability, focused attention, and relevance were relatively low. However, in the subdimension of confidence and perceived learning, the average score was quite high. The value of user satisfaction on the usability aspect is 90%, while the level of satisfaction on the player experience aspect is lower at 76%. So that the overall level of user satisfaction is 81%. This proves that this game gets a positive response from users.

Keywords— augmented reality, educational game, English, pronunciation, ghost, smartphone, android.

I. INTRODUCTION

Current technological developments have a considerable influence on life. One of technology that has both positive and negative impacts is the widespread use of smartphones in Indonesia. Smartphone active smartphone users in Indonesia are currently more than 100 million people, making Indonesia the fourth largest smartphone active country in the world after China, India and America [1].

Among these smartphone users, many of them are students. Although many parents provide smartphones for them as a

means of communication and appropriate entertainment, but not a few of these students who use smartpone as a medium of excessive entertainment. The results of research on the level of game play addiction in the area of Jatinangor Sumedang showed that as many as 38% of respondents included in the category of no addiction and 62% of respondents included in the category of addiction. Based on these studies it was also concluded that the level of addiction occurred in school-age children [2].

Due to the high level of addiction, there were not a few students who underestimated their obligations, namely international language learning, English language. Based on the demographics issued by EF (English First), it was concluded that the level of English proficiency in Indonesian society is low, with an EF score. The EPI is 52.15, which is ranked 10th out of 20 countries in Asia, and is ranked 39th out of 80 world countries [3].

To solve these problems, one of the solutions provided is to build games that can benefit the players. In order to give an interesting impression to serious educational games, the impression of fun must be prioritized. For that, given a feature in the game that has become a game trend today. Based on Infoholic Research, the AR Gaming market is expected to reach \$ 284.93 billion in 2023, with a growth estimate of 152.7% during the 2017-2023 period. Improving AR integration into mobile devices, online population growth and innovation in technology in games, forcing many people to integrate AR into their traditional games. Increasing online gamers and internet penetration are some additional factors that contribute to market growth [4].

Many researches have been done to prove the usefulness of Automatic Speech Recognition technology in English pronunciation and improvements. Yao (2015) carries out an

intervention study on two middle school classes with similar English pronunciation level. The results shows that the EFL learners who learned through Speech Visualization Technology had better performance and showed greater favor in this learning method. Xu (2010) also does a similar research and the results shows that an ASRbased CAPT software — My English Tutor is useful for Chinese college learners to improve their segmental quality.

Based on several problems that have been explained previously, in this study a game called "The Demite" will be built which will provide solutions not only as a means of entertainment for the people of Indonesia, but also as a means of learning in pronunciation of English words. This game is a casual-horror genre with an Augmented Reality feature that requires the player to capture and fight ghosts by saying English words that appear with the right pronunciation. With this game, it is expected that players can learn how to speak English correctly.

II. ANALYSIS AND SYSTEM DESIGN

II.1 User Needs Analysis

II.1 Analysis of The Demite in General

II.1.1 Game abstract

The Demite, taken from Indonesian word Dedemit which means a spirited creature that haunts and disturb people [5], usually become a myth among the inhabitants of Indonesia's rural areas, villages even in the city's notoriously haunted areas, is a location-based augmented reality horror game inspired by Pokemon Go. The game utilizes the player's mobile device's GPS ability to locate, capture, battle mythical creatures, called The Demite, which appear on the screen as if they were at the same real-world location as the player. To catch *The Demite*, voice command in English is used, so this game is also used as a learning medium in speaking English.

II.1.2 Objectives to be achieved by the game

Learn to pronounce English words and sentences correctly.

II.1.3 Game justification

This game not only for entertainment purpose only, but also can help player to learn to pronounce English with fun

II.1.4 Core gameplay

Players need to catch or kill ghosts by saying the English words that appear on screen.

II.1.5 Game features

The main features of this game are location-based, augmented reality, and speech recognition.

II.1.6 Genre

This game genre is a casual educational game with a little element of horror.

II.1.7 Number of players

Singleplayer.

II.1.8 Target platforms

Android smartphone with a working internet connection and a rear camera.

II.1.9 Game theme

Horror game that introduce variety and uniqueness of Indonesian ghost.

II.1.10 Player characteristics

Anyone with minimum basic knowledge of English pronunciation.

II.2 Ghost Type Analysis

Ghosts used in the game The Demite are ghosts that are very popular in Indonesia, that so many horror films and games use ghosts as in-game objects and characters in films. The popularity of horror films in Indonesia has never subsided, always having its own place for Indonesian film lovers. In 2017 alone, various horror film titles gained millions of viewers. Some of the most popular ghosts in Indonesia include pocong, tuyul, kuntilanak, sundel bolong, buto ijo and gondoruwo.

II.3 Design of Game Architecture

II.3.1 General System Design

The Demite basically uses client server system which can be seen in Figure 1. In client side, player uses smartphone's camera to view AR objects, and its microphone to detect player's voice using voice recognition. It also uses GPS to pinpoint player's location and Gyroscope to get device's orientation. While in server side, OpenStreetMap framework is used to get map data. SQLite and MySQL also used to retrieve user's data and word's database.

Figure 1. The Demite architectural design.

II.3.2 Database Design

In this application, the database is used as a medium to store the data about users and ghost objects. In the project planning, the database used is MySQL.

Figure 2 The Demite database design.

II.3.3 Rancangan *Gameplay*

When the first time a player opens a video game application, the player will be presented with a login view that will require the player to fill in a username and password. If the player does not have an account, then the player is required to create a new profile that will be used to log in.

After the player successfully log in, the player will be presented with the Map Scene which is using Augmented Reality screen that shows ghost locations in the real world. The Map Scene displays the number of coins, refresh button and ghosts based on the location of the player. If the player does not encounter ghosts at all, players can move locations by walking in the real world, then press the refresh button to update the player's current location. After the player starts moving in the real world, players will be able to find ghosts. When the closest ghost is visible, the player can click on the ghost, which will then enter the Catch Scene.

Figure 3. The Demite general gameplay Flowchart.

Catch Scene is shown when players fight ghosts. This displays in Augmented Reality technology to give the player an immerse impression. In this mode, players can fight ghosts. To fight the ghost, players must say English words. If the words spoken are true, then the ghost's Health Points will decrease, and vice versa. If the player having difficulty to say these words, the player can use buy hints using coin.

Figure 4. Interface design of Catch Scene.

Catch Scene has several objects shown in Figure 3.5. The interface description is as follows:

1. Ghost profile
Showing the name of the ghost and the it's HP bar.
2. Ghost
Representation of ghost objects that are being fight.
3. English words
Words used to attack ghosts, when the player spells this every word correctly the ghost's HP will decrease.
4. Hint button
Used to give a hint in the form of audio pronunciation of the word. If a hint is used, the player's coins are reduced.
5. Coin
Number of player's coins.

When the HP ghost is zero, it means the ghost has been defeated and the player will enter the Score Scene to see the status of the ghost that has been defeated, the money earned, and see the results of the assessment. Then the player returns to the Map Scene. If the player wants to continue playing, the player can choose other ghosts to fight. If not, the player can log out of the game .

II.3.4 Design Characteristics of Ghosts

There are many types of Indonesian ghosts, but in this game, only the most famous ghosts are used.

1. Pocong Pute

Description: the soul of a dead person trapped in its shroud (*kain kafan*).

Attributes:

- Appearance: The dead body covered in white fabric tied over the head, under the feet, and on the neck.
- Health points: 20
- Speed: 1
- Ghost level: 1

2. Si Tuyul

Description: a small child spirit invoked by a dukun from a dead human fetus using black magic.

Attributes:

- Appearance: The dead body covered in white fabric tied over the head, under the feet, and on the neck.
- Health points: 40
- Speed: 5
- Ghost level: 2

3. Nyai Sundel Bolong

Description: Sundel Bolong is the soul of a woman who died during childbirth and the baby came out from her back.

Attributes:

- Appearance: Woman with beautiful long hair and a long white dress. She has a large hole on her back.
- Health points: 60
- Speed: 4
- Ghost level: 3

4. Mba Kunti

Description: Spirits of women who was raped when she was alive, then died while pregnant.

Attributes:

- Appearance: pale-skinned women with long black hair, red eyes, and white dress smeared in blood
- Health points: 80
- Speed: 4
- Ghost level: 4

5. Mas Buto Ijo

Description: Commonly asked for help by shamans and paranormal to bring great amount of money and wealth fast.

Attributes:

- Appearance: Tall and big, green skin, long hair.
- Health points: 100
- Speed: 3
- Ghost level: 5

6. Mbah Gondoruwo

Description: Spirits of man who died and doesn't accept his own death.

Attributes:

- Appearance: Big human-like apes with a reddish black skin colour, his body is covered with thick hair growing all over the body.
- Health points: 120
- Speed: 4
- Ghost level: 6

Following is a description of each attribute in a ghost:

- Appearance: shows 2D and 3D assets created.
- Health points: commonly called by its abbreviation which is HP, it will decrease if the ghost is attacked.
- Speed: the speed of a ghost when they avoid player's attack

- Ghost Level: The higher the level of the ghost, the higher the ghost's HP.

II.3.5 Design of English Pronunciation Learning

A child will not be able to speak if they are not given the opportunity to express what he has heard [30]. One way to learn English pronunciation is to listen and imitate. So before learning to speak, they must learn how to listen. Learning English pronunciation in The Demite is located in the Catch Scene, which is when the player fights a ghost by saying English words. On the display in the Catch Scene there is a hint button. This button is used to play audio pronunciation of English words to say to fight the ghosts. So that the player can listen carefully, then imitate it.

In the Score Scene, the results of the pronunciation that has been done on the ghost will be shown. Players can review the errors so that players can learn and not make the same mistakes.

Figure 5. Interface design of Scene Score

It can be seen in Figure 5 that the player say three words in the fight against ghosts pocong pute. The words that must be spoken are *cruel*, *proud*, and *chair*. But the player only say one correct word, which is *chair*, while the other two words are wrong. Determination of damage value is calculated from the difficulty level of the word. The harder the word is to say, the more damage is given to the ghost. Damage calculations are not discussed in this study and will be discussed in related studies.

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

III.1 Implementation of Interface and Gameplay

The following are the results of implementation of interfaces and gameplay based on the designs compiled in the previous chapter. Figure 6 shows the appearance of the splash screen, loading scene, and main menu. All three are displayed

sequentially at the beginning when the application is opened.

Figure 6. Interface of splash screen, loading scene, dan main menu.

Figure 7. Ghost spawning based on location on the Scene Map (left), and Catch Scene with Pocong Pute (right).

Figure 8. Score Scene after defeats Gondoruwo

In the Scene Map, ghosts spawned randomly through the AR display. When the ghosts appear in the Scene Map, the player must click on one of the ghosts to fight, then the catch scene will be displayed (Figure 7) to fight the ghost. When a player wins against a ghost, the scene score will be displayed (Figure 8). There are two views in this scene, status tab and result tab.

III.2 Functional and System Testing

Functional and systems testing is video game testing to find out whether the entire menu, scene, buttons, speech recognition, ghost spawning, and English words have functioned as they should, by trying to carry out these functions one by one then the results are observed. The results of this functional test showed that the implementation of the entire menu, scene, buttons, speech recognition, ghost spawning, and English words had gone according to plan.

III.3 Player Testing

III.3.1 Sampling

Testing is done by giving questions to 32 high school students consisting of 5 men and 27 women.

Figure 9. Gender and age group graph of game tester

III.3.2 Results of the Testing Questionnaire

The questionnaire provided is based on the MEEGA model. The MEEGA model is intended to be used in case studies with a one-shot post-test only design, where case studies begin with the user playing an educational game, then the MEEGA questionnaire is answered by students to collect data. The following is a list of statements given to the player or tester, which was submitted after they tried playing The Demite game. The results of the questionnaire were calculated using a Likert scale.

Figure 10. Results of the testing questionnaire with usability as quality factor

Figure 11. Graph of average usability questionnaire assessment

Based on Figure 10 and Figure 11, it can be seen that the average rating of numbers 1, 4 and 5, which are included in the *aesthetic* and *learnability* subdimension, are relatively low. This shows that most players find it difficult when they first learn how to play this game. In addition, the average rating for question number one that is low indicates that the aesthetic value of this game is relatively low.

Figure 12. Graph shows the results of the testing questionnaire with the player experience as a quality factor

Figure 13. Graph shows the average player experience questionnaire assessment

Based on Figure 12 and Figure 13 , it can be seen that the average scores of numbers 20, 21, and 22, which are included in the *focused attention* subdimension, are very low, as seen from the average value that is less than zero. The definition of focused attention itself is the brain's ability to focus its attention on the target stimulus for any period of time. This shows that this game failed in terms of attracting players to focus when playing this game.

The average score of number 23 which is included in the *relevance* subdimension is also relatively low indicating that the game content is not relevant to the interests of players.

Conversely, the average rating of numbers 10 and 29 is the highest value among the others. Number 10 is subdimension *confidence* . This shows that the content and structure of this game helps players become confident that players can learn with this game. While number 29 is the subdimension of *perceived learning* . This shows that the game contributes to the English pronunciation of the player.

III.3.3 User Satisfaction Level

To measure the level of satisfaction of the users of The Demite game, calculation is done using the following formula..

$$H = \frac{Z}{J} * 100 \%$$

- H = User Satisfaction Level
- Z = The number of respondents' answers to each question
- J = Number of respondents

The number of respondents' answers to each question (Z) is how many users give the rating *agree* and *strongly agree*. While the number of respondents (J) is the number of respondents but by overruling respondents with neutral answers. Neutral options can be seen as an easy option to take when the respondent is unsure, but whether the choice is truly neutral or the respondent does not answer is still questionable [31].

Figure 14. Graph shows the level of user satisfaction on aspects of *usability* and *player experience*.

If the value of user satisfaction is distinguished based on the aspects of *usability* and *player experience*, then the results can be seen that the level of satisfaction on *usability* aspects is greater at 90%. While the level of satisfaction on the *player experience* aspect is lower at 76%. So that the overall level of user satisfaction is 81%.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results that have been achieved during the design and testing process educational *game* can be concluded as follows.

1. Modeling of educational games learning English pronunciation *The Demite* has been implemented and

succeeded. The design of ghost characteristics based on the design of *video game* architecture has also been successfully implemented.

2. The results of the student questionnaire analysts showed that the average subdimension assessment of *usability*, namely *aesthetic* and *learnability*, and the subdimension of the *player experience*, namely *focused attention* and *relevance*, were relatively low. However, in the subdimension of *confidence* and *perceived learning*, the average score was quite high.
3. The value of user satisfaction on the *usability* aspect is 90%, while the level of satisfaction on the *player experience* aspect is lower at 76%. So that the overall level of user satisfaction is 81%. This proves that this game gets a positive response from users.

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